

Domain Expert Panel: Challenges and Opportunities

Author(s):

Alessandro Giovannucci (Chaos League)

Mafalda Morganti (Chaos League)

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About the project - Larpocracy

Larpocracy researches spaces for deliberation and democratic skill building through live-action role-playing (larp). Funded by Horizon Europe, seven leading partners will study the use of larp as a method for creating inclusive and democratic social spaces, both online and offline.

Our mission is to investigate the potential of live-action role-playing (larp) as a method to foster democratic skill building and political engagement. Our research aims to leverage this innovative form of co-creative embodied play to address declining engagement in traditional democracy and the limitations of social media in fostering civic discourse.

The project will produce:

- Studies and experiments chartering capacities of larp in supporting democratic engagement and fostering democratic skill-building.
- Public events in collaboration with designers and organizers from marginalized and vulnerable communities.
- Design exemplars of larp and larp spaces capable of supporting inclusivity and democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Democracy by Design Toolkit.
- A widespread community of Experts understanding the capacities of larp and larp-like spaces in fostering democratic engagement.
- Evidence-based Policy Recommendations supporting policymakers in multiple domains.

Executive summary

This report presents the first-year experience of engaging the Domain Expert Panel (DEP) within Work Package 6 of the Horizon Europe project Larpocracy. The Domain Expert Panel brings together professionals working in larp-adjacent fields ranging from education to cultural institutions, artistic practice, and civic engagement. Their role within the project aims to provide external perspectives that can inform the research and design activities across the different Work Packages, as well as to act as “emissaries” exploring the potential application of the project’s methods and insights within their own professional contexts and practices.

The deliverable focuses on the initial phase of the engagement process and the lessons emerging from the first year of implementation. It presents the strategy adopted and the activities implemented for the DEP, analyses the challenges encountered in sustaining its participation and outlines the adjustments to the engagement model that have been identified for the next implementation phases of the project.

The activities documented in this report include preliminary one-to-one meetings with DEP members aimed at mapping expertise and expectations, the participation of the panel in the pan-project symposium in Uppsala (March 2025) and follow-up initiatives designed to connect the DEP with the ongoing work of the consortium.

This initial phase brought to light several structural and organizational challenges in maintaining consistent involvement of the DEP. These included the difficulty of aligning the panel’s participation with the evolving timelines of the Work Packages, the diversity of expectations and availability among DEP members, as well as the limited opportunities for sustained interaction within the consortium due to their roles as outside experts.

The process highlighted the importance of adopting a differentiated, multi-level approach capable of accommodating varying levels of availability, expertise, and institutional contexts. As the project progresses and a growing number of events, activities, and deliverables become available for experimentation and feedback, new opportunities are emerging for the DEP to engage more directly with the work of the consortium. In this perspective, linking participation to practical experimentation and concrete activities is expected to support stronger involvement from panel members, enabling them to relate project insights to their own professional environments. The DEP can also further develop as a collaborative interface between research and practice and as a space for shared learning.

In addition, the discussions with the DEP helped identify several key thematic challenges and areas for further exploration, including:

- designing larp experiences that foster transformation and democratic learning;
- supporting the transferability and institutional adoption of larp-based methods, which in turn supports Larpocracy work on policy recommendations;
- reaching and including diverse and politically heterogeneous audiences;

- strengthening facilitation skills and capacity building for practitioners.

1. Introduction

The Horizon Europe project Larpocracy investigates the potential of live-action role-playing (larp) and participatory methods as tools for fostering democratic engagement and developing democratic skills. Within this framework, the project engages not only researchers and designers, but also practitioners and experts working in fields adjacent to larp practice. An important element for this engagement is the Domain Expert Panel (DEP), a group of professionals representing a wide range of domains where participatory methods may contribute to democratic engagement.

The DEP was conceived to connect the research and design activities of the project with practitioners working in different professional environments, operating as a collaborative interface between the project and a broader ecosystem of cultural, educational, and civic organizations. Through their professional experience, panel members bring perspectives from fields such as museums, education, participatory arts, civic engagement, and game design. Their influence on the project strengthens Larpocracy's exploitation strategies and provides valuable input towards the project's policy development work.

This model of engagement reflects a broader understanding of research as a participatory and co-creative process, where knowledge is generated not only within academic contexts but also through dialogue with practitioners and communities of practice. In this sense, the DEP can be understood as a model of engagement that supports mutual learning between research and practice, enabling the project to test and reflect upon the potential applications of its methods across different domains.

Within the project, the DEP fulfils a double role. On the one hand, the panel provides feedback and perspectives that can inform the direction of the research and design work as well as the development of toolkits and policy recommendations, that is conducted within the different Work Packages. On the other hand, panel members act as "emissaries" within their own professional environments, reflecting on how the approaches explored in the project may be applied, adapted, or tested within their organizations and fields of expertise.

The present deliverable focuses on the first phase of implementation of the DEP within Work Package 6, which is responsible for coordinating the engagement of external experts within the project.

1.1 Aim and scope of this document

The aim of this report is to document and analyze the initial phase of engagement of the DEP within the Larpocracy project. In particular, the report focuses on the first year of implementation of the panel and examines how its role as an interface between research and professional practice has begun to take shape.

The document describes the engagement strategy adopted to involve the panel members, the activities carried out during the first year, and the main challenges encountered in maintaining consistent interaction between the panel and the consortium. It also identifies the lessons learned from this initial phase and outlines improvements to the engagement strategy in order to strengthen the role of the panel in the next stages of the project.

The report highlights as well thematic insights and questions that emerged from the exchanges with the DEP, particularly during the first pan-project symposium. These reflections provide an initial indication of the broader issues that practitioners encounter when attempting to apply larp-based and larp-adjacent methods within different institutional and professional contexts.

While this document does not aim to present final conclusions or evaluations of the panel's long-term impact, it provides a first overview of the engagement process and contributes to the ongoing reflection on how participatory and co-creative collaboration models can support research and innovation projects.

1.2 Profile, fields and expertise of the DEP members

The DEP brings together professionals whose work intersects with participatory methodologies, immersive experiences, and democratic engagement. It includes the following members:

- Erica Gangsei is Director of Interpretive Media at the San Francisco Museum of Modern Art (SFMOMA), where she leads the development of educational multimedia experiences. She is also the founder of the museum's Play SFMOMA initiative, exploring the use of games and playful interaction for audience engagement and learning.
- Katrin Anne Geneuss is Senior Lecturer in Education at Ludwig-Maximilians-Universität in Munich, Germany. Her work focuses on hybrid learning environments and innovative teaching methods in language education.
- Adam Norman is a project leader at Kalmar County Museum in Sweden and works with the international organization Bridging Ages, which develops "time travel" educational experiences inspired by historical role-play.
- Mohamad Rabah is the founder and organizer of Bait Byout, a children's larp organization in Palestine that develops participatory storytelling experiences for young participants. During the course of the project he was joined in the panel by Tamara Nassar, who collaborates with the organization on educational and participatory initiatives.
- Josephine Rydberg is a CrossMedia developer in the Gävleborg region in Sweden and a PhD student at Stockholm University of the Arts, researching the dramaturgy of participatory experiences in immersive environments such as virtual reality.

- Bart Simon is Professor at Concordia University in Canada and Director of the Milieux Institute for Arts, Culture and Technology. His research focuses on game cultures, immersive theatre, and experimental media environments.
- Maria Saridaki is a game studies researcher specializing in rituals, play, and spaces of transformation. She directs Trust in Play: School of Urban Game Design, which explores how participatory play can address social issues and civic engagement.
- Gijs van Bilsen is a trainer, speaker, and consultant working in organizational development and leadership training through participatory simulations. As managing partner of Live Action Learning, he develops experiential learning formats and serious games for professional development and civic engagement.

1.3 Profile, fields and expertise of the DEP members

The motivations of the DEP members for joining the project reflect their shared interest in participatory methodologies and their potential to support social reflection, learning, and democratic engagement.

Several panel members highlighted a particular interest in the transformative potential of participatory and immersive experiences. In this regard, Bart Simon asked during the preparation of the symposium: *“How can participatory performance be transformational for perception and action?”* reflecting a broader motivation to understand how participatory formats can create situations in which participants reconsider their perspectives and engage with social issues through embodied interaction.

Others were particularly interested in the design challenges involved in creating such experiences. Maria Saridaki, for example, raised the question: *“How can we design play formats that balance intent and structure with open, transformative experience?”*. This reflects an interest in understanding how participatory environments can create space for dialogue and exploration while still providing sufficient structure to guide participants through complex themes.

Additional motivations relate to the application of participatory methodologies within institutional and educational contexts. Katrin Geneuss asked: *“What are the possibilities and limitations of education for democracy in formal settings?”* Similarly, several participants raised questions concerning the practical implementation of these approaches within organisations. Adam Norman highlighted the need to better understand how the impact of participatory experiences can be evaluated, while Gijs van Bilsen pointed to the challenge of institutional adoption by asking: *“How do we get local institutions to actually run our larps?”*.

Together, these reflections illustrate how the members of the panel approach the project from complementary perspectives, combining interests in design, facilitation, institutional adoption, and

democratic learning. Many of these motivations and questions later informed the thematic areas of reflection discussed in Section 3.5 of this report.

1.4 Methodological approach

The document addresses and builds upon the following guiding questions to analyze the first phase of engagement of the DEP and to outline directions for its further development:

- How can the Domain Expert Panel function as an effective interface between research, design experimentation, and toolkit and policy development within the Larpocracy project, and professional practice in relevant fields?
- How can the engagement model be adapted to support meaningful participation, exchange, and experimentation throughout the duration of the project?

The main sources of information include the individual exploratory meetings conducted with panel members during the initial mapping phase, the presentations and discussions that took place during the first pan-project symposium in Uppsala, and the follow-up meetings and exchanges organized in the months following the event. These interactions provided an opportunity to gather reflections from the panel members on their professional contexts, which were then integrated also by internal reflections within the Work Package teams regarding the implementation of the engagement strategy and the adjustments that emerged from the experience of the first year.

2. Engagement strategy and implementation

2.1 Preliminary mapping phase and alignment of expectations

The engagement of the DEP started with the implementation of a preliminary mapping phase, aimed at establishing direct contact with the panel members individually and gaining a clearer understanding of their expertise, interests and expectations regarding their involvement in the project.

Between the end of January and the beginning of February 2025, we organized a series of one-to-one online meetings with each of the 8 members of the panel. These meetings, conducted by Chaos League's team for WP6, typically lasted between 45 and 60 minutes and served both as an introduction to the project and as an opportunity to explore potential connections between the professional activities of the experts and the themes addressed within Larpocracy.

This preliminary phase was particularly useful for identifying the diversity of profiles represented within the panel. During these conversations, we presented the objectives of the project and the role envisioned for the panel, while inviting the experts to share their experience with larp or other larp-

adjacent methodologies, as well as the contexts in which they work. We also discussed practical aspects of participation, such as possible opportunities to test or apply project insights within their own professional environments.

2.2 Participation in the Uppsala Pan-project Symposium

The most relevant moment of engagement with the DEP during the first years was the first pan-project symposium, which took place in Uppsala, Sweden, from 24 to 26 March 2025. The event brought together members of the Larpocracy consortium, the Advisory Board and the Domain Expert Panel, as well as participants from the wider larp and research communities.

Seven out of the eight members of the DEP attended the symposium in person, while one member joined some of the sessions online. Their participation included presentations, discussions, and participatory activities organized as part of the symposium program. In preparation for the symposium, we invited the panel to prepare a short presentation introducing themselves and their professional background. We asked each member to prepare a short presentation addressing three main points: their professional profile and connection to the themes of the project; key challenges or insights from their field that could be relevant to Larpocracy and one question or idea they would like to explore within the project. The intention behind this was to better understand the perspectives and questions brought by the DEP, while also creating a starting point for discussion within the panel.

These presentations were shared during the first WP6 session of the symposium on 24 March 2026. The session allowed Domain Experts to become more familiar with each other's backgrounds and areas of expertise. From our perspective, the symposium played an important role in strengthening the connection between the DEP and the project. It created opportunities for informal exchanges and networking, allowing the members to share reflections on the themes emerging from the project and to explore possible areas of collaboration with different Work Packages.

DEP members also contributed to the public launch event of Larpocracy which took place on the same day at the Humanistiska Teatern. In particular, Tamara Nassar, creative director of the Palestinian larp organisation Bait Byout, participated in the panel discussion "Larp in an Age of Stressed Democracies," reflecting on the role of participatory experiences in contexts marked by political and social tensions. Another DEP member, Josephine Rydberg, contributed to the panel "Privilege and Participation," which explored how issues of access, diversity, and participation shape both larp and deliberative democratic processes.

As the only moment during the first year when the panel members could interact directly in person with the consortium and with each other, this first symposium represented a central reference point in the engagement process. This experience also provided useful insights and reflections into how the involvement of the DEP could be further strengthened in future events. During the WP6 session, the presentations were primarily shared within the panel itself, rather than being integrated into a

broader discussion with the consortium. In retrospect, this format limited the opportunity for direct exchange between the panel and the wider project team.

2.3 Post Symposium mapping and follow-up

Following the first pan-project symposium in Uppsala, we continued the engagement process by exploring possible ways to connect the DEP more directly with the work taking place in the different Work Packages.

As an immediate follow-up to the symposium, we organized an online meeting with the panel a few weeks after the event. The aim of this meeting was to revisit the main takeaways from the symposium and to explore more concretely which Work Packages and thematic areas each expert felt most interested in engaging with. During the meeting, we invited the panel to reflect on the topics presented during the symposium and to indicate where they believed their expertise and professional experience could be most relevant within the project.

During this phase, several panel members also expressed an interest in gaining a deeper understanding of the background and objectives of the Larpocracy project. In response, a shared online folder was created containing key resources about the project, including relevant documents, presentations, and background materials. The intention was to provide the panel members with a clearer overview of the project and to support their ability to engage more meaningfully with the work of the consortium.

A dedicated Slack channel for the DEP was created as well, to facilitate ongoing communication and provide a space where panel members could easily interact with the WP6 team and with each other between project events.

2.4 Challenges in engaging the Domain Expert Panel

While the activities described above allowed us to establish contact with the DEP and initiate the collaboration, our experience during the first year also revealed several practical challenges affecting the continuity and depth of engagement. These challenges were not unexpected, considering the exploratory nature of the project and the diversity of professional contexts represented within the panel. However, they highlighted several structural conditions that influenced how and when the experts could interact with the work of the consortium.

2.4.1 Alignment with Work Packages timelines

During the first year of the project, most of the Work Packages devoted a significant amount of time to internal organization and coordination, including defining research approaches, establishing working procedures and setting up the collaboration structures within the consortium. As a result, many activities were still in an early developmental stage during the period when the initial engagement with the DEP took place.

Until late fall, only a limited number of design experiments and deliverables were available that could be shared with the panel for discussion or experimentation. This meant that interactions with the DEP remained largely exploratory and focused more on understanding their perspectives and areas of expertise than on engaging them directly with specific project activities. In some cases, this created a sense of distance from the project's day-to-day work from the perspective of the panel members, highlighting the importance of carefully aligning the timing of external engagement with the stages of development of the Work Packages.

2.4.2 Diverse profiles, expectations and availabilities

Another challenge relates to the diversity of profiles and expectations regarding the forms of participation and the potential outcomes of their involvement represented within the DEP. While this diversity represents a valuable resource for the project, it also influenced the extent to which individual panel members could participate in meetings and project activities during the first year.

The geographical distribution of the panel members also introduced practical constraints for organizing meetings and collective activities. The DEP includes members spanning several time zones across the United States, Canada, the Middle East and different European countries. Coordinating meeting times that could accommodate participants across these different time zones proved challenging and limited the number of occasions in which all members could participate simultaneously.

2.4.3 Limited opportunities for ongoing interactions

In the timeline of the project for this first year of implementation, opportunities for direct interaction between the panel and the consortium were limited to a very small number of project events. The pan-project symposium in Uppsala represented the only large-scale gathering during this phase where panel members could interact directly with the consortium and with each other.

The consortium also experimented with a few informal online activities, such as reading circles and playing circles, intended as spaces for shared exploration of larp-related materials and experiences. However, while these initiatives were important for the consortium members in the initial phase of the project, they only had a limited number of iterations and were discontinued as the project moved on from its initial phase into a phase of intense practical work in the research work packages.

While communication tools such as the shared resource folder and the dedicated Slack channel helped maintain contact, organizing regular collective moments proved more difficult. One key factor

that influenced the flow of interaction relates to the fact that the DEP operates outside the formal structure of the consortium. As external contributors, panel members do not have direct access to the project's internal collaboration platforms, such as the consortium SharePoint environment or the different Slack channels used by the project partners to discuss the Work Packages workflow. Neither would these channels be of use for the DEP members due to their communication intensity. This limited the development of sustained dialogue among panel members and the consortium and made it more challenging to establish the panel as an active space for exchange during this initial phase.

3. Lessons learnt and adjustments to the engagement strategy

Our experience so far provided plenty of valuable insights into how the engagement of the DEP can be strengthened in the next phases of the project. While the initial activities made it possible to establish relationships with the panel members and explore their interests and expertise, the challenges identified within the previous chapter highlighted several conditions that influence how external experts can most effectively interact with the work of the consortium.

Following internal discussions within the WP6 team and exchanges with the project steering group, these reflections informed several adjustments to the engagement strategy and led to the development of a more structured yet flexible model for the involvement of the DEP.

3.1 Multi-level engagement model

As observed during the initial meetings and the symposium, panel members expressed different preferences regarding the type and intensity of their involvement. Some experts showed interest in actively contributing to applied research activities, participating in playtesting, or supporting empirical work. Others expressed a stronger interest in contributing through reflection, thematic discussions, or reviewing project outputs. A third group preferred to remain informed about the progress of the project without having to commit to regular participation.

These observations led to the formulation of a multi-level engagement model, designed to accommodate different forms of participation while maintaining a shared connection with the project. The proposed structure distinguishes between three levels of involvement:

- Light involvement, focusing on staying informed through milestone meetings and periodic updates;
- Moderate involvement, including opportunities to review project outputs, participate in thematic discussions and provide feedback;

- Active involvement, involving participation in applied research activities, pilot initiatives, or playtesting processes.

This structure was communicated to the DEP at the beginning of the second project year together with a proposed timeline of activities and events, allowing members to select the level of involvement most compatible with their interests and availability.

3.2 Defining timing and clarity of engagement

Another key lesson relates to the importance of clearly identifying moments within the project timeline when the DEP can engage with the work of the consortium. To address this, the new engagement strategy introduced a clearer structure, allowing panel members to plan their participation more effectively and ensures that their contributions can be connected to specific moments in the development of the project.

The proposed calendar includes several opportunities for engagement throughout the year, such as:

- Milestone meetings bringing together the panel and the consortium to review project developments and upcoming activities;
- Thematic meetings focusing on specific topics related to the work of the project;
- Participation in project events, including symposia, festivals and design activities;
- Annual wrap-up and planning sessions, providing an overview of progress and identifying future directions.

The proposed timeline for the second year includes a yearly kick-off meeting which took place at the end of January 2026, both milestone and thematic meetings scheduled throughout the year, participation in two in-person pan-project symposia (Poland and UK) and an annual wrap-up session aimed at reviewing progress and planning future activities.

3.3 The value of engagement through practical application

Many panel members expressed interest in understanding how the approaches explored within Larpocracy could be applied in their own professional contexts. However, during the initial phase of the project relatively few concrete activities were available that could support this type of engagement. As the project progresses, a growing number of events and participatory formats are being organized, including festivals, design activities and testing opportunities for larp-based methods. These initiatives create opportunities for the DEP to engage with the project through direct experience and experimentation.

Early examples of this type of engagement have begun to emerge. For instance, Gijs van Bilsen participated in the online design retreat in late February (Larpocracy Larp Design Jam) organized within the frame of Work Package 5, contributing to the exchange of perspectives between practitioners during the activity.

Participation in such initiatives allows panel members to observe and experience the methodologies explored within the project in practice, while also providing the consortium with feedback grounded in professional experience. This type of engagement strengthens the action-research dimension of the panel and creates stronger connections between the research activities of the consortium and the professional environments represented within the DEP.

3.4 Integration of the DEP as learning community

During the symposium and follow-up meetings, it became evident that the value of the panel does not lie only in the feedback provided to the consortium, but also in the opportunity for panel members to encounter and learn from each other. This observation highlighted the importance of supporting the panel not only as an advisory structure for the project but also as a peer-learning environment. In practical terms, this means creating opportunities where the DEP can exchange perspectives, reflect collectively on project activities, and discuss how the approaches explored within Larpocracy relate to challenges emerging in their own fields of practice.

The communication infrastructure established during the first year provides a basis for supporting this type of exchange. In particular, the Slack channel can serve not only as a space for sharing updates and materials, but also as a platform for more ongoing discussions between the DEP and members of the consortium. Opening this space to broader interaction across the project team can facilitate informal exchanges of ideas and the identification of connections between the work of the different Work Packages and the expertise of the panel members. In this perspective, the DEP can gradually develop into a learning community that contributes to the broader goal of translating the project's insights into diverse real-world contexts.

3.5 Identified key challenges, insights and further areas of exploration

Beside informing adjustments to the engagement strategy, the exchanges with the DEP also generated several reflections on the broader challenges related to the use of larp and participatory methodologies in different professional and institutional contexts.

Several of these reflections began to emerge already during the preparation of the first pan-project symposium, when the experts were invited to prepare their presentations introducing the key

challenges, insights, and questions from their respective fields that could be relevant to the work of Larpocracy. These contributions provided an initial overview of the perspectives and areas of interest brought by the panel and served as a starting point for further discussion during the symposium itself.

Building on these presentations and the conversations that followed during and after the symposium, a number of recurring themes began to take shape. Rather than representing definitive conclusions, the themes outlined in the following paragraphs should be understood as areas of ongoing exploration that can inform the work of the project in its next phases. They reflect both the professional perspectives brought by the panel and the challenges encountered when attempting to translate participatory and larp-adjacent practices into different environments, and will be immensely valuable for the development of the project's future outputs, including the Democracy by Design Toolkit and the policy-oriented activities planned in Work Package 7.

3.5.1 How to design larps that foster transformation and democratic learning

One of the questions raised by the DEP concerns the design of participatory experiences capable of supporting meaningful reflection and transformation among participants. Larp is inherently oriented toward collaboration and collective exchange. Through their characters and within a shared fictional context, participants interact with one another, negotiate decisions, and often step into perspectives different from their own. The combination of role immersion and collective play can therefore support the development of empathy and the exploration of complex social dynamics. From a design perspective, this potential depends on the careful relationship between narrative structure, participant agency, and facilitation.

Several discussions highlighted the importance of agency, understood as the participant's capacity to make meaningful choices within the experience. Designing for agency requires balancing structure and openness: larp formats must provide sufficient scaffolding to guide participants through the experience while still leaving space for exploration, improvisation, and emergent interaction. This balance is particularly relevant when designing experiences aimed at democratic learning, where the objective is not to transmit predetermined conclusions but to encourage participants to explore different viewpoints and reflect on social and political dynamics.

Participants in the discussions also highlighted the value of designing scenarios that confront participants with ethical dilemmas or ambiguous situations where no single solution is clearly "correct". Such narrative situations can function as mirrors of real social dynamics, allowing participants to explore the consequences of different choices and to engage with questions of responsibility, power, and collective decision-making.

Several reflections also pointed to the fact that the design process itself can represent a form of democratic practice. Developing a larp often involves collective negotiation among designers and facilitators, requiring listening, deliberation, and shared responsibility. These practices can inform the ways in which democratic principles are translated into participatory formats experienced by players. At the same time, some contributors also raised questions about how emerging technologies, including AI-assisted tools, might influence future forms of participatory design and facilitation.

These reflections mirror well the key research questions addressed by the research work packages (WP2-WP5) and influence their studies and design explorations.

3.5.2 How to support transferability and institutional adoption of larp based methods

While immersive and participatory formats can generate strong engagement among participants, educational and cultural institutions often face practical barriers when attempting to adopt such approaches. One structural reason for this is that larp remains only partially professionalized and therefore lacks widely shared operational standards that could facilitate its adoption across different organizations. As a result, many existing methodologies rely heavily on tacit knowledge and practitioner experience, which can be difficult to translate into institutional environments where clear procedures, documentation, and accountability structures are required.

One strategy discussed within the consortium concerns the development of resources that support replication and adaptation. Examples include case studies, practical guides, and modular design frameworks that allow practitioners to adapt larp-based methods to their own contexts. Documenting design choices, as well as common challenges or mistakes, can help organizations better understand how such experiences may be implemented under their specific operational conditions.

During the exchanges with the DEP, several typical institutional concerns were also identified, including time constraints, budget limitations, safety protocols, authorization procedures, and evaluation requirements. Addressing these issues may require the development of implementation models that support gradual adoption, for example through pilot projects followed by adaptation and scaling within organizations.

Another recurring insight concerns the role of “multipliers” or internal champions within organizations who can support experimentation and encourage the adoption of participatory approaches. Identifying individuals willing to test and adapt these formats within their own institutional environments may significantly facilitate organizational uptake.

3.5.3 How to reach and include diverse and politically heterogeneous audiences

Another important theme emerging from the discussions concerns the challenge of engaging audiences that are socially, culturally, and politically diverse. In such contexts, the objective of participatory experiences is not to convince participants of a particular position, but rather to create conditions where individuals with different perspectives can coexist within a shared experience, engage in dialogue, and reflect on democratic questions through interaction.

During the discussions, panel member Maria Saridaki formulated this challenge clearly by asking: *“How can larp reach the unreachable, politically diverse audiences, break social media bubbles, and stay inclusive?”* This question highlights the difficulty of designing participatory formats capable of engaging individuals who may not normally participate in civic or cultural initiatives.

One aspect discussed concerns the risk that participatory experiences primarily attract audiences already familiar with larp or similar formats. Addressing this challenge requires careful attention to how such activities are communicated and presented. Reducing specialized terminology or insider language can help make participation more accessible to newcomers and individuals unfamiliar with participatory play. The discussions also emphasized the importance of identifying potential barriers to participation. Even when participatory formats are theoretically open to a wide range of audiences, practical factors such as costs, location, time commitment, or a perceived sense of “not belonging” may discourage participation from certain communities. Mapping audience groups and identifying these barriers may therefore represent an important preliminary step in designing inclusive participatory initiatives.

Some practical approaches discussed include developing “low-threshold” participation formats and having inclusion extended beyond recruitment and embedded throughout the entire experience. Creating safe and supportive environments where participants feel able to express themselves without fear of judgement is essential for enabling meaningful interaction among individuals with different perspectives. From this perspective, the design and facilitation of participatory experiences must carefully consider both the narrative structure of the activity and the social conditions that allow diverse groups to interact constructively.

3.5.4 How to support capacity building and facilitation skills for larp practitioners

A final area of reflection concerns the skills and competencies required to design and facilitate participatory experiences effectively. Within the discussions, it was emphasized that the quality and impact of larp-based experiences depend not only on the design of the scenario but also on the capacity to facilitate the human processes that unfold during the activity. In many contexts, however, facilitation skills are developed informally through “learning by doing,” mentoring, or oral transmission within practitioner communities. While this experiential learning is valuable, it may also create inconsistencies in practice and uncertainty among institutions or practitioners, representing a barrier to the wider adoption of larp-based approaches.

The exchanges with the DEP also raised questions about the role facilitators play in connecting fictional experiences with real-world reflection. For example, panel member Adam Norman raised the question of whether immersive experiences risk leaving participants “*content, passive, or even indifferent to things happening in our world.*” This reflection highlights the importance of facilitation practices that support participants in processing their experiences and linking them to broader social and democratic questions.

Addressing these challenges may therefore require strengthening capacity-building initiatives for practitioners, including training activities and “train-the-trainer” approaches that support the development of facilitation skills, as this may play an important role in enabling the broader diffusion and long-term sustainability of larp-inspired methodologies across cultural, educational, and civic domains.

Conclusions

In this document, we have documented and reflected on the first phase of implementation of the DEP within the Larpocracy project. What emerges is a very clear picture: the panel is not an “add-on” to the project, but one of its most promising pieces of infrastructure. In an initiative like Larpocracy, the presence of professionals from all these diverse backgrounds is what allows the consortium’s assumptions to be continuously tested, preventing the work from remaining confined within a self-referential horizon. The DEP is already functioning as a threshold, where different languages meet and begin to translate one another, making visible what is truly transferable and what instead remains implicit and rooted in community practices.

At the same time, the experience so far has shown that this threshold must be facilitated and sustained with the same care as any participatory experience. The difficulty of aligning timelines, expectations, and availability is not a bump in the road, but a structural condition: the panel exists outside the consortium’s organizational machinery, and for that very reason it needs an engagement model that is clear and able to value different kinds of contributions. Adopting a multi-level approach is therefore not merely an operational adjustment, but a necessary step to make collaboration sustainable over time and to prevent participation from becoming a burden and turning it instead into a meaningful opportunity for exchange.

The reflections presented in this report also identified several thematic challenges that may inform the next phases of the project, including the design of transformative larp experiences, the transferability of larp-based methodologies to institutional contexts, the engagement of diverse audiences, and the development of facilitation and capacity-building practices. As the project progresses and a growing number of design experiments, events, and participatory activities are implemented, the DEP is expected to play an increasingly important role as a space where research

insights and professional practice can meet, supporting the development of the project's future outputs and contributing to the broader goal of translating larp-based approaches into practical tools for democratic engagement.

About the Authors

Alessandro Giovannucci is an award-winning larp designer, co-founder of Chaos League, and Professor of History of Music at the Conservatory of Teramo.

Mafalda Morganti is a freelance trainer, facilitator, Learning and Development consultant, and member of the Italian collective Chaos League.

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The Larpocracy Consortium

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Chaos League A.P.S. (Italy)